

MAJOR GROWTH CHALLENGES FACED BY BANGLADESHI E-COMMERCE STARTUPS

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Abstract

E-commerce in Bangladesh has become a disruptive force in the new normal. However, compared to developed countries, the sector is still in infancy. Many companies are struggling to grow and several big ones have shut down recently. Although the e-commerce sector has attracted attention from different stakeholders, there has been little research that explored the challenges while trying to grow in Bangladesh. This qualitative study investigates the major growth challenges e-commerce companies in Bangladesh are facing and probable solutions. In-depth interviews with six e-commerce entrepreneurs and industry experts in this study revealed that the major challenges that affect the growth of e-commerce are funding, finding the right talent and supply chain. The findings add value in the existing literature in South East Asian countries having similar environment factors and ecosystems. This study is expected to help founders and other stakeholders to prioritize solutions to tackle the growth challenges in e-commerce.

Keywords : *E-commerce, Funding, Growth Challenges, Supply Chain, Talents.*

1. INTRODUCTION

In the new global economy shaped by social distancing and work from home culture, electronic commerce or e-commerce has become a critical business model all over the world. Helping vendors to deliver products and provide services in a much more effective and superior way than traditional channels, e-commerce is at the heart of a new distribution channel (Lee, Pi, Kwok & Huyanh, 2003). UNCTAD (2002) shows that a significant number of developing countries have included e-commerce in their national e-strategies for the development of e-commerce.

Bangladesh's startup ecosystem is known as the untapped digital goldmine of Asia, and e-commerce has become a disruptive force in that ecosystem shaped by social distancing and work from home culture. The rapid growing economy of Bangladesh recorded an impressive annual GDP growth rate of 8.1 percent in 2019, which is the highest in the country's history and in South Asia for 2019. As an emerging economy, Bangladesh has embraced technology at a rapid pace with 98 percent mobile phone connection, 62 percent internet penetration, 102 million+ people on the internet with 94 million mobile internet penetration (Lightcastle Partners Report, 2020). With the increased number of internet users and growing popularity of online shopping, e-commerce is one of the most prospective sectors to grow in Bangladesh.

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Driven by increasing discretionary income, technology adoptive consumers, literacy rate, effects of globalization, middle income societal enhancement and rapid urbanization, e-commerce in Bangladesh is growing rapidly (Lightcastle Partners, 2016). In terms of e-commerce revenues, Bangladesh is ranked 46th in the global ranking. Currently there are 2,000 e-commerce sites and 50,000 Facebook based outlets which deliver around 30,000 products every day (Lightcastle Partners, 2020). About 80 percent of these online sales are concentrated in Dhaka, Chattogram and Gazipur. According to the report by Lightcastle, e-commerce market is expected to grow to US\$3Bn by 2023. The application of e-commerce is different in Bangladesh than it is in China, Europe and America because of the social and cultural difference, overwhelming popularity of traditional business models, typical consumer behaviors, and consumer expectations. f-commerce (Facebook Commerce) is very prominent in Bangladesh, which is defined as selling of products or services through Facebook (Valles and Petrova, 2012).

In recent years, many Bangladeshi organizations are trying to build physical infrastructures to support the development of e-commerce and mimic e-commerce model from western countries. The present Government of Bangladesh aims at making digital Bangladesh. The Government is therefore initiating different e-commerce programs. However, compared to developed countries, Bangladesh's e-commerce is still in its infancy and not many companies are growing exponentially. Many e-commerce companies started with high promise, yet few already left and many are stuck in the old system as we failed to build up the e-commerce ecosystem and address issues that would eliminate these problems. Though the landscape is changing, we are not doing it fast enough (Islam, 2020) and there's little research to identify the challenges that are hindering the growth of e-commerce. Hence, a study to identify the growth challenges e-commerce companies in Bangladesh are facing, as well as outlining solutions is necessary. This study attempts to identify the major growth challenges e-commerce companies in Bangladesh are facing, and to outline solution for the major growth challenges faced by e-commerce companies in Bangladesh.

The paper has the following parts: first, it reviews the extant literature relevant to e-commerce growth in Bangladesh, starting with important definitions. Then, the research methodology is discussed in detail. Next, the findings are presented and summarized. After that, discussion on findings is provided with recommendation. Then, limitations of the study is pointed out. Finally, the article is concluded pointing out the contribution and future search scope.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Definitions

Turban, Leidner, McLean and Wetherbe (2008) defined e-commerce as the process of buying, selling, transferring or exchanging products, services or information via computer networks, including the internet. According to OECD (2011), the definition

of e-commerce stands as - “the sale or purchase of goods or services, conducted over computer networks by methods specifically designed for the purpose of receiving or placing of orders.” F-commerce (Facebook Commerce) is defined as selling of products or services through Facebook (Valles and Petrova, 2012).

2.2 E-commerce Business Types

Upasna and Rebello (2014) mentioned e-commerce transactions can be segmented into three broad categories or modes, based on participants involved in the transaction: **Business to Consumers (B2C)** is the business model where business sells products or services directly to consumers. Bangladesh e-commerce started with and revolves around B2C mostly. **Customer to customer (C2C)** is a business model where customers can trade with other customers in an online environment. Auctions and classified advertisements are two implementations of the C2C model. **Business to Business (B2B)** is the model where a company conducts commercial activity online and the customer is another business.

2.3 E-commerce in Developing Countries

Developed countries adopt e-commerce very slowly and majority of them just linger in the lowest level of sophistication in this regard (Migiro, 2006; Sam and Leng, 2006). When adopting e-commerce, developing countries face different challenges than developed countries (Molla and Licker, 2005), as they often lack appropriate financial, legal and physical infrastructure which is a prerequisite, as well as sometimes they need to deal with cultural stigma which hinders the applicability of e-commerce (Hemple and Kwong, 2001). Organizational factors also considered as the most prevalent hindrance toward adoption of e-commerce in developing countries (Kartiwi and MacGregor, 2007). Technological factors of e-commerce adoption include compatibility, complexity, relative advantage, usefulness and ease of use (Grandon and Pearson, 2004), and the environmental factors are customers or suppliers, partners, alliances, pressure from competitors, image of internet technology; the role of government and users' expectations (Aguila-Obra and Padilla-Melendez, 2006).

2.4 E-commerce in Bangladesh

Though the journey of e-commerce in Bangladesh started in the late 1990s, the sector is still in the developing phase compared to the developed countries. At the beginning, small numbers of Bangladeshi expatriates used e-commerce services as a channel to send gifts and books to relatives, especially in the capital city. Later in the years 2001-2008, while the e-commerce industry was booming globally, it experienced little slow pace growth in Bangladesh due to lack of knowledge and infrastructure. After several failed ventures, the situation has started changing in 2012-2013 when few more dedicated players introduced themselves in the market with strong determination. Also the customers had negative perceptions about e-commerce, like prices are higher than retail, products are not same as picture etc. Eventually the customers' negative perception around the sector started to diminish and started

getting good appreciation from the early adapters, mainly located in Dhaka. The potential of the e-commerce industry not only enticed business entrepreneurs but also few foreign investors joined the competition along with local ones.

A study by Statista demonstrates that in 2019, the Bangladesh e-commerce industry stood at \$1,649 million, rising to \$2,077 million in 2020 and is predicted to touch \$3,077 million in 2023. Currently there are 2,000 e-commerce sites and 50,000 Facebook based outlets which deliver around 30,000 products every day (Lightcastle Partners Report, 2020), where 80 percent of online sales are concentrated in Dhaka, Chattogram and Gazipur. The transaction amount was 491.4 Core Tk in June 2020, which increased to 640.4 Core Tk in July 2020 (Bangladesh Bank).

Online retail stores having B2C models are the most widespread form of e-commerce sites present in Bangladesh. As the country and culture has evolved so has the taste of its inhabitants, this led to the boom in the restaurant business and home food delivery. Also the ever growing busy life, dual earning nuclear family, heavy traffic in the urban areas have impact on increasing home delivery. Grocery Stores like Chaldal.com, with funding from 500 Startups, serves as the most renowned online grocery store in Bangladesh where consumers can order groceries online and it will be delivered to them. Retail chains like Meena Bazaar and Swapno also opened up their own online grocery order and delivery service sensing customer demand (Lightcastle Partners, 2019)

3. RESEARCH GAP, OBJECTIVE AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Gap

Although adoption of e-commerce is a well established research topic in developing countries, surprisingly a few researchers in Bangladesh have addressed the issue instead of having growing public interest in the sector. Hoque (2008) identified several challenges that influence the adoption of e-commerce in Bangladesh, such as infrastructure, awareness of customers about e-commerce, government support and legal framework which influence the adoption of e-commerce in Bangladesh. Azam (2007) examined the effects of buying culture and infrastructural forces in implementing B2C e-commerce in Bangladesh and reported that buying culture of the country's citizenry is negatively related to the implementation of B2C e-commerce in Bangladesh. Hossain, Ali, Kibria and Bhuiyan (2013) found that B2C e-commerce in Bangladesh is not flourishing because of low per capita income, inadequate infrastructure, legal issues, lack of trust between business and consumers. Hasan and Huda (2013) discussed the challenges of the e-commerce adoption and its solution, as well as the effectiveness of e-commerce in the financial sector of BD, but did not focus on finding the growth challenges. Although many researches have been done on factors affecting the adoption of e-commerce for developing countries in the 2000-2010, which was the beginning of the e-commerce era worldwide, there has been little research on the topic in the last few years. Also, there has not been much research that focuses on the next phase of adoption of e-commerce for developing countries like Bangladesh, focusing on growth stages.

3.2 Research Objective

From the above perspective, this study is focused on the following objectives:

- To identify the major growth challenges e-commerce companies in Bangladesh are facing
- To outline solution for the major growth challenges faced by e-commerce companies in Bangladesh

3.3 Research Methodology

The research was conducted from a Relativist Ontology and Interpretivist philosophical perspective, where reality is subjective and considered to be constructed within the human mind. Since identifying growth challenges and solutions is a complex topic, a deep understanding of experts' opinion was needed. Thus an inductive research approach was taken and a Qualitative method was applied as it is a powerful tool to explore those complexities, (Clifton & Handy, 2001) and allow respondents to grasp respondents' own view towards this matter. Qualitative method is also known to produce a wealth of detailed data on a small number of individuals (Patton, 1990).

Using non-probabilistic convenience sampling, six (6) e-commerce industry experts were selected for semi-structured in-depth interviews, which included e-commerce company founders, e-commerce parcel delivery company founders, investors and representatives from E-commerce Association of Bangladesh (e-Cab). The fieldwork started with B2B and B2C e-commerce company founders, then based on the findings and analysis from them, more interviews were conducted with Venture Capitalist, e-commerce courier company founder and e-Cab director to get better understanding of the growth challenges mentioned in the earlier interview.

Semi-structured interviews were selected because they not only give interviewers some choice in the wording to each question but also in the use of probes (Hutchinson and SkodolWilson 1992). To maintain social distancing, the interviews were conducted virtually over zoom and took 30 - 60 mins for each interview. Secondary data sources for the research were previous research, official statistics from published reports, historical data and information, reports of some prestigious consulting firms, books and other relevant published documents. Limited literature on e-commerce startups was found in terms of growth, and challenges for the sector in Bangladesh.

4. FINDINGS

Analyzing the collected data, the major challenges that affect the growth of e-commerce can be divided into three broad issues - Funding, Supply Chain and Finding the Right Talent.

4.1 Funding

All the respondents interviewed considered funding as a major challenge for growth as E-commerce is inherently a cash hungry business. Globally, large e-commerce companies have raised huge funds during their operation, and many have raised

funds even before starting. Examples include companies like Amazon, Alibaba, FlipCart in India, Tokopedia in Indonesia, etc. As this is a new and emerging sector in Bangladesh, building the ecosystem is even more expensive as huge investment is needed to build infrastructure like transportation and delivery hubs, to educate people regarding the advantages of online shopping, etc.

Challenges in Getting Funds

Trust: Besides being a new sector, it is also difficult to make people trust an e-commerce company. In e-commerce, lots of subsidies or incentives are needed so that a person can try out a product. This is how FinTech companies like Bkash acquired customers, but it is difficult for E-Commerce as they lack the inflow of cash at the early stage of business.

Scale up problem: For e-commerce companies which maintain inventory, there is additional cost associated with that, as one of the respondents mentioned:

“We are a hybrid model e-commerce. We have our own products, as well as partners’ for which we have to maintain a certain level of inventory. If we think of a cycle to maintain inventory stock for one to two months, it needs an investment cash fund to hold that inventory.”

Difficulty in raising investment in the sector: The respondents think that compared to few other tech-startup sectors, it is very difficult to raise investment for e-commerce startups. When a startup ecosystem is growing in an emerging economy, the first vertical to rise is e-commerce since the business model is comparatively simple, value chain is easier and it is the basic demand of customers who want convenience shopping. But the model gets complicated when e-commerce startups start scaling up, the inventory gets bigger and supply chain becomes complex.

Liquidity crunch due to Cash on Delivery (COD) system: In Bangladesh, there are lots of f-commerce running alongside e-commerce. The concept of f-commerce is not a western concept, rather it is a local concept. So traditionally our online shopping behaviour is different, our e-commerce industry is primarily constituted of SME categories of entrepreneurs. Customers often do not differentiate between f-commerce and e-commerce, so the overall online shopping industry operates bit differently than those of developed countries. Another big difference in online shopping from western countries is that Cash on Delivery (COD) method is very popular in Bangladesh; almost 80-90 percent parcels are delivered through COD. One reason here is trust factor, as culturally customers still do not trust paying advance via online payment. Also, the number of credit card users is very low in our country. Besides, due to previous bad experiences with low quality products, especially at the early stage of the industry, customers still do not want to pay until they receive the product. The dependence on COD payment creates a cash liquidity crisis for e-commerce companies, since they have to wait longer to retrieve the payments from delivery companies.

Scrutinizing the above issues, investors do not find e-commerce in Bangladesh an attractive business model to invest in. Local investors are often unwilling to invest as they do not understand the e-commerce business. A good source of investment can be local conglomerates; with their existing business knowledge and financial backbone, they can enter in e-commerce themselves or support like-minded companies. However, not many local conglomerates have invested in e-commerce. As local investors are not funding, foreign investors are also skeptical to fund e-commerce.

According to one of the respondents,

“The first question foreign investors ask is why are not local investors investing and why should we invest if local investors are not investing. We have to explain Bangladesh to foreign investors first, because they are not aware about our country. Further, they need to know the E-commerce market size, the problem, the customer group then the potential. A foreign investor does not want to spend more than 15-20 minutes while investing 2-3 million dollars. By that time, we try to explain the benefit to investors who are not aware of the Bangladesh market, they have already lost interest.”

Another big issue is, investors do not see e-commerce as a mature industry yet and want the market to grow more. Besides, e-commerce normally has a high failure rate. It requires a huge deep pocket to make an e-commerce venture really successful and the initial entry to barrier seem less costly. Usually one or two players dominate the market, they take 80 percent and the rest of the companies share 25 percent. Where there is a foreign player like Alibaba, a global giant backing up Daraz, it is more unattractive for others to invest.

Also, E-commerce normally takes a long time to be profitable as seen in global players like Amazon (took 10 years) and also local big players in Bangladesh. Venture Capital (VC) fund life is on average 7 years, and VCs intend to exit after that period with a significant high ROI. Also there is no clear legal guideline or policy in Bangladesh on how an investor will invest the money and receive the return. Angel investors, who invest in the early stage, normally think short terms and want to exit after 2-3 years when VCs take over the shares. But since the overall investment cycle is not yet steady for e-commerce, they are unwilling to invest as well.

Bank is another entity that can invest in e-commerce. But the problem with financing by banks is that banks want to see physical assets. But the e-commerce entrepreneurs only have talent as an asset, not physical asset. Also banks can easily go to a Garment business and give 10 times bigger loan than an e-commerce, so they do not need to hustle after multiple companies.

Solving funding issues

According to the respondents, there are no quick solutions to solve the mentioned challenges, and these need to be solved with patience allowing enough time. All the stakeholders need to work together to solve these problems, like the Government

and others. Government support is needed not for money only, but for all kinds of administrative roles, supply and distribution, and decision making.

Local Investors and Conglomerates: Local investors are often unwilling to invest as they do not understand the e-commerce business. To solve this, they can deploy fund managers or consultants who will manage this on their behalf. Local conglomerates can come forward and invest in promising e-commerce or set up themselves.

Government Role to bring in foreign investment is same as above: the respondents think it is time to prioritize e-commerce by the government and allocate funds for this sector.

“The Government already has a startup fund, and then can help e-commerce to get funding from there. If four or five startups are successful from that, it will become a success story. In an average startup, there can be 33 x return, so that can work. But it needs to be invested appropriately.”

“Say a foreign investor invests in the local startup, the government will then invest a similar amount in the same valuation in that startup. So the government does not have to do the due diligence etc, they are just using piggybacking. This model has been successful in Singapore and Korea. But we have to keep in mind that both Singapore and Korea have better control and regulations.”

The Role Banks can play: The e-commerce entrepreneurs only have talent as an asset, not physical asset. Banks need to change this mindset and policies, believing that in future, the e-commerce industry will grow and give huge return on investment.

Having attractive business models: For last few years, e-commerce with a bit different model than traditional B2C got funded. Investors think these models have a bigger chance of succeeding than traditional models. So e-commerce companies can rethink their business model and solve customers’ pain points in innovative ways which can attract investors’ interest.

4.2 Supply Chain

According to the respondents, another major challenge for the growth of e-commerce is supply chain. They mentioned there are challenges for both ends of the supply chain.

Sourcing

Bangladesh is predominantly an import dependent economy. E-Commerce is too small in Bangladesh to make large scale import work. Importers don’t bring products for e-commerce separately, rather they import for their primary customers which are retail business owners. So when an e-commerce company wants to get those products, it either needs to purchase from retailers or wholesalers with comparatively higher price, or they do not get the product at all.

Delivery

Predominantly E-Commerce worldwide is B2C driven. And a customer does not always necessarily want to wait 3-4 days for a product just to avail a 5-10 percent discount which he can purchase immediately from a retail and get instant gratification. But in Bangladesh the e-commerce delivery is not yet ready for last mile delivery. The e-commerce logistics companies are heavily dependent on traditional companies like S.A Paribahan or Sundarban to deliver parcels at remote places, where the customers need to collect parcels from their hub and no home delivery is available. Huge investment is needed to improve logistics and delivery, along with skilled personnel for planning.

However, one respondent, the courier company founder, mentioned -

“The logistics industry is not new here and there are already systems in place where large FMCG companies make their products available to the most remote places in the country. For different services, different logistic processes are needed, and the same goes for e-commerce. The problem is, e-commerce companies are not automated to reduce workload from courier companies. This often results in customers not receiving products on time, making the delivery costly.”

Since in Bangladesh, Cash on Delivery (COD) is the most popular payment method for e-commerce, the control is mostly on the customer, not on the delivery company. There are often fake customers, sometimes the mobile number is switched off and the customer is not available.

Another issue is when an e-commerce companies take orders, they do not always take detailed shipping info and alternative mobile numbers. Besides, packaging often becomes an issue if the e-commerce company does not pack the product properly and it gets damaged on transportation.

Overcommitment from e-commerce companies often creates a headache for courier companies, like committing to deliver within two days anywhere in the country whereas in reality, delivering to remote places outside Dhaka may take 3-7 days sometimes.

The cost of delivery is another big problem. For a compliant courier company, the cost of service would be higher than a noncompliant courier company. There are many courier companies operating in the country without proper license, offering cheaper rates but at the end forced to leave due to low service quality and customer dissatisfaction. This creates an unhealthy competition on price and ultimately the compliant courier companies suffer and bleed money. The shipping charge standard is set very low, making the e-commerce delivery service unattractive to reputable courier companies like DHL or FedEx.

“Cash on Delivery is also a problem for a courier company. We are good at delivering, not at managing cash and accounts. Often the product and cash get hijacked from the delivery man. The rate of transaction charge we keep is also very low at 1 percent and

not sufficient, even MFS companies like bKash charge more for each transaction.” - said the courier company founder.

Solving the Supply Chain Challenges

The respondents suggested that the sourcing problems can be fixed if the demand can be increased, and to increase the demand, someone needs to play aggressive. Then to solve the delivery issue, roads and transportation systems need to be developed, more delivery hubs need to be created at strategic points, and bringing in skilled people is also very important.

“In China, different Logistic Companies built a consortium which helped them to deliver everywhere. This model can help with better management and also can charge a bit premium if needed. Research says customers are willing to pay up to 17% extra to get product faster.”

Since it needs huge investment, the government can fund initially along with a few big investors in a collaborative way. To solve the trust issues which are obstructing prepayments, escrow accounts can be established with help from third party financial institutions. In this way the customer will pay while ordering, but the merchant will not get it until the customer receives the product, is satisfied and did not ask for a refund within a specific period. This will increase customers' responsibility and reduce effort and cost for couriers.

“E-commerce market in Bangladesh is based in China. We can build local industry, improve manufacturing and procurement which will help e-commerce and overall economy. If we can build an ecosystem where we can get products from someone from a remote village and can deliver that to a customer directly then it will strengthen our e-commerce and economy.”

4.3 Finding the Right Talent

Leadership Roles

According to the respondents, finding the right personnel for a specific role is another major challenge affecting e-commerce growth in Bangladesh. Building and running a business needs smart people at the top, who can take decisions, make great plans and direct the team to execute the plans. Though there are people like that in Bangladesh, they are not yet willing to come to e-commerce because the reward is not that much compared to the established industries.

“We see in the garment industry we often have top management from outside Bangladesh, say from India and Srilanka. For a startup it is difficult to meet their demands, so we cannot bring in people like them until they really want to be part of a startup.”

One of the respondents reflected on the topic differently, saying that the e-commerce owners in Bangladesh themselves need to develop leadership qualities to bring in better talents and lead them.

Technological Skills

There is a lack of people with solid technological skillsets who are willing to work in e-commerce.

“In Bangladeshi culture we still somehow lack the quality to understand user experience properly. Historically we are powerful in RMG, but we cannot do the design. we are good at replicating; we are not good when it comes to innovation... that is my realization.”

Solving the problem of finding right talent

To build up skilled people, different stakeholders like the Government, e-Cab, BASIS can work together to build up training facilities. As e-commerce is a new sector, collaboratively they can bring in expert people with years of experience to guide the e-commerce founders and leaders. Next, there can be e-commerce specific courses, training on overall entrepreneurship, strategic thinking, consumer drive, digitalization along with other skill development programs.

5. DISCUSSION ON FINDINGS

The findings from this exploratory research resonate with the LightCastle Partners (2020) report stating that finding the right talents and access to financing are the top problems for emerging startups. According to that report, funding in Bangladesh as a percentage of GDP is 0.04 percent, which is significantly low compared to other SouthEast Asian countries like China (0.074 percent), India (0.51 percent) and Indonesia (0.3 percent) but higher than Pakistan (0.01 percent). The Government of Bangladesh can play a significant role to support the industry and help them overcome the challenges mentioned by developing infrastructure, allocating sufficient funds, facilitating required training and formulating policies. The Government of Bangladesh (GoB) has also deployed the National ICT Policy in 2009 to become Digital Bangladesh by 2021. Government policies and projects from the ICT Ministry, such as IDEA Project and Startup Bangladesh Limited with 100 crore BDT (US\$ 11.5 Million) funds, are taken to improve the local startup ecosystem (LightCastle Partners, 2020). These can be increased and substantial focus can be given to e-commerce since this is the first sector in the startup industry that grows in an emerging economy.

While the e-commerce founders are keen to get funds to support their venture, they need to remember that source of funding affects the organizational culture of e-commerce ventures, which in turn has its impact on the recruitment as well. Venture capitalists, when investing in e-commerce, are often keen on enhancing the brand image of the company so that they can get quick returns on their money. This often leads to hiring the ‘big names’ rather than hiring based on competencies (Hamilton, 2001), which may create a ripple effect on the organizational culture and impact recruitment and retention as well. Crowdfunding, a form of crowdsourcing and alternative finance, can be considered as an option as well, which is yet not that popular and in effect in Bangladesh.

As the e-commerce businesses start to achieve scale and grow in Bangladesh, tackling the last mile logistics is of immense importance. As GoB is setting up 28+ Hi-Tech Parks, including infrastructure support like data centers, to support technology companies (LightCastle Partners, 2020), they can also focus on reducing traffic congestion in the major cities, building transportation and other relevant infrastructure which all the logistics companies can use.

The findings showed that people in Bangladesh still do not trust e-commerce companies completely, which creates a barrier to use prepayment methods like debit/credit card or mobile financial services. Building trust among Internet users helps e-commerce sites to develop a strong relationship with them (Fang, Qureshi, Sun, McCole, Ramsey & Lim, 2014; Thakur & Summey, 2007; Miremadi, Hassanian-Esfahani & Aminilari, 2013). Instead of focusing entirely on lucrative discount deals, which often results in failure to deliver according to the promise and lead to a dip in brand image, more focus should be given on enhancing customer experience.

Lack of trust in the technical and institutional environment can hamper the adoption of e-commerce (McKnight, Choudhury & Kacmar, 2002 and Kim and Benbasat, 2009). As customers do not get the chance to investigate online products, there is a fear of purchasing them (Mitchell, 1999; Lwin and Williams, 2006), which can be mitigated by providing product warranty. Replacement options or Product warranty can be also provided to increase prepayments, which is one of the key elements of competitive strategy (Udell and Anderson, 1968).

Getting the right talent was a major challenge found in the study. Bangladesh has 62 percent+ under 35 years tech adaptable young population, 5,000+ IT students graduating each year creating a strong group of entrepreneurial waves focused on solving critical problems, and the country's median age of 27.9 years means more young people are willing to take risks and explore innovations in the economy (LightCastle Partners, 2020). All stakeholders, like e-commerce companies, Government, e-Cab etc need to work together to create awareness among and young professionals towards joining in e-commerce workforce highlighting the future prospect of the sector and globalization opportunity. Careful and robust selection programs for hiring high-quality and motivated employees need to be devised by the e-commerce companies, which fosters the growth of entrepreneur-led organizations (Joshi and Srivastava, 2015).

E-commerce startups are technology driven, so companies need to look for incumbents who are updated and have the traits to suit a technology startup. NASSCOM (2016) report suggests that required skills for e-commerce start-ups include risk-taking attitude, innovative mind-set, flexible to work hours and cross-functional expertise. It also suggests that start-ups need mature and adaptable professionals. Individual competencies, flexibility, networking and innovation capacity are the key attributes besides other factors that play an important role for the success of entrepreneurial ventures (Forster, Parrar & Woss 2013). Government regulations have a significant influence on the macroeconomic performance of market economies and thus it

is necessary to devise proper regulations for establishing a business in a country (Nicoletti and Pryor, 2006). There is an urgent need to have necessary laws and regulations for online businesses in place by discussing with different stakeholders to make sure both companies and customers are benefited.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

- **E-commerce Policy:** With the Digital Bangladesh agenda in Government's core, it is of foremost importance to form an e-commerce policy to offer multiple benefits for the e-commerce industry and ecosystem players such as VAT/Tax exemptions and rebates, loans and investment facilities etc. An enabling policy will attract foreign investment in the sector, increase employment rate and foster the growth of e-commerce and overall economy.
- **Work in collaboration with all transport related ministry:** To transform the whole country into a single marketplace where every house is a destination, combined effort is needed.
- **Fund of Funds:** ICT ministry and Startup Bangladesh collaborating with public and private sectors can form a fund of funds to invest in e-commerce. The fund will make downstream investments in venture capital and alternative investment funds.
- **Investor Benefits:** The government needs to ensure an investment friendly environment in Bangladesh like updating Foreign Exchange Regulation Act 1947, introducing TAX benefits, reducing entry barriers, and ease repatriation of profits of foreign investors.
- **Industry-Academia Collaboration:** To set up the right kind of infrastructure, industry-academia collaboration is mandatory to nurture innovation and prepare talents for the industry.
- **Fulfillment centers at strategic points:** To effectively increase delivery quality, existing retailers and conglomerates with established fulfillment centers and supply chain networks can collaborate with e-commerce companies to leverage their facilities.
- **Integrate order tracking systems:** All e-commerce companies should update their tech backend that will be beneficial for customers, delivery companies and the e-commerce business.
- **Omni channel presence with retail stores:** Having strategic retail storefronts can help simplify logistics and inventory, and can be achieved through strategic partnerships.
- **Strengthen training and awareness raising programs:** To understand e-commerce and its implications, nationwide awareness programs need to be organized along with skill development trainings, strategic thinking, overall entrepreneurship courses, etc.

7. LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

This study focused on the major growth challenges for the overall e-commerce industry from a macro point of view, there might be other growth challenges for individual companies based on their type and from a micro point of view which was not researched here. There are a large number of f-commerce shops running in Bangladesh, which may face similar or different growth challenges which were not studied here. Next, the interviewees answered the questions related to growth challenges based on their own experience and knowledge, so the findings are subjective.

8. CONCLUSION

In this study, we strived to identify the major growth challenge faced by Bangladeshi E-commerce and recommended solutions. According to the findings from the research, the major challenges that affect the growth of e-commerce are Funding, Finding the Right Talent and Supply Chain. E-commerce is inherently a cash hungry business, and as a new sector, huge investment is needed to build infrastructure, create awareness among customers and incentivize them to purchase online. The lack of interest from local and foreign investors due to lack of proper policies and regulatory issues, uncertainty on return on investment and few other issues make this sector unattractive to investors so far. Logistics is another major challenge, having two facets of the problem - supply side and delivery side. Since Bangladesh is predominantly an import dependent economy, most of the products need to be imported from outside, which becomes difficult for local e-commerce considering the small scale of business. Delivery is also a challenge due to traffic congestion in major cities, lack of proper transportation network to facilitate last mile delivery and lack of trust from customers which hinders prepayments. Finding the right personnel for leadership and technical roles is also a major challenge as found in the study. There's still a lack of personnel with proper technical skills needed for a high growth e-commerce. As a new sector with comparatively lower compensation offered due to lack of funds and with much higher risks than established businesses, it is difficult to onboard people in leadership or managerial positions. All the stakeholders related to the e-commerce ecosystem can work together to solve these challenges which can increase employment rate and foster the growth of e-commerce and overall economy.

This research adds value to both practical and academic fields and addresses the research gap mentioned earlier. One of the research gaps mentioned was lack of study on growth challenges faced by Bangladeshi e-commerce, which this study identified, narrowed down and also recommended solutions. This adds value in the existing literature of the relevant field. Since Bangladesh represents a fine alignment with the emerging market typology and has similar environment factors and ecosystem with some of the South-East Asian countries, the findings can be extended to other emerging countries which are similar to Bangladesh. In practical field, this study is expected to help different e-commerce stakeholders by prioritizing solutions accordingly.

This study focused on the major growth challenges faced by e-commerce companies from a macro point of view, future research can be conducted to identify specific growth challenges faced by different types of e-commerce business, like grocery, fashion, food, etc. Since this study was focused only on e-commerce and excluded f-commerce completely, a separate study can be done to find challenges faced by f-commerce businesses in Bangladesh which is very unique in the global e-commerce context. Customers play a crucial role in e-commerce, future research can address issues like current customer perception towards e-commerce. A comparative study among e-commerce and other startup business models in terms of growth and prospect can be also interesting. Since this study was conducted using a qualitative method, another quantitative research on the similar context can be conducted to identify different factors and variables that impact each of the major challenges found in the study.

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